

Fig S3. Illustration of kernel functions used to generate artificial cell tracks driven by a Hawkes process. **(Left)** Temporal kernel $g_1(t)$ with varying arrival intensity $\alpha > 0$ and exponential decay rate $\beta > 0$. **(Middle)** Spatial Kernel $g_2(\theta)$ with varying concentration parameter $\kappa_M \geq 0$. **(Right)** Hawkes Intensity $\lambda(t, \theta)$ with background intensity $\lambda_0 = 1$ for varying θ along the cell contour and the following choice of parameters: $\alpha = 0.4, \beta = 0.5$, and $\kappa_M = 100$ as used in our model.